

Source: [Heravi, M. M.](#), Lashaki, T. B. Fattahi, B. Zadsirjan, V. (2018). Application of asymmetric Sharpless aminohydroxylation in total synthesis of natural products and some synthetic complex bio-active molecules, RSC Advances, 8(12) [doi: 10.1039/c7ra12625e](#).

Application of asymmetric Sharpless aminohydroxylation in total synthesis of natural products and some synthetic complex bio-active molecules

[Majid M. Heravi](#)¹, Tahmineh Baie Lashaki¹, Bahareh Fattahi¹, Vahideh Zadsirjan¹

¹ Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Physics & Chemistry Alzahra University, Vanak, Tehran, Iran.

Abstract

Sharpless' report illustrates the application of Asymmetric Sharpless Aminohydroxylation (ASHA) in the stereoselective synthesis of vicinal amino alcohols as important intermediates in the total synthesis of complex molecules and natural products with significant biological activities. The ASHA allows the regio-syn-selective synthesis of 1,2-amino alcohols via reaction of alkenes with salts of N-halosulfonamides, -amides and -carbamates employing osmium tetroxide (OsO₄) as an efficient catalyst. In this reaction, chirality is induced via the addition of dihydroquinine- and dihydroquinidine as derived chiral ligands.

Keywords: Hydroxylation, Ligands, Molecules, Osmium compounds, Stereochemistry, Stereoselectivity, 1,2-amino alcohols, Aminohydroxylation, Bioactive molecules, Complex molecules, Efficient catalysts, Osmium tetroxide, Selective synthesis, Stereoselective synthesis, Synthesis (chemical)